

Impact of NITDL and Customs and Excise Duty on Corporate Investment of Information and Telecommunication Companies in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of the National Information Technology Development Levy (NITDL) and Customs and Excise Duties on corporate investment in Nigeria's information and telecommunication sector. The rapid expansion of the telecommunications industry has positioned it as a critical driver of economic growth, innovation, and digital transformation in Nigeria. However, the sector continues to face multiple fiscal obligations that may influence investment decisions. The study adopts a quantitative research design, relying on secondary data obtained from annual reports and relevant industry publications of eight quoted telecommunications companies in Nigeria as of 31st December 2022. The sampled firms include Airtel Africa Plc, MTN Nigeria Communication Plc, CWG Plc, Chams Holding Company Plc, E-Tranzact International Plc, NCR (Nigeria) Plc, Omatek Ventures Plc, and Briclink Africa Plc. Purposive sampling technique was employed, while multiple regression analysis using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) was used to examine the relationships among the variables. The findings reveal that both the National Information Technology Development Levy and Customs and Excise Duties exhibit a negative but statistically insignificant relationship with corporate investment in the sector. This suggests that although increases in these tax components are associated with reductions in investment levels, the effects are not strong enough to be statistically meaningful. The study concludes that taxation, in its current structure, does not significantly determine corporate investment decisions in Nigeria's telecommunications industry. Instead, other macroeconomic and structural factors may play more dominant roles. The study recommends improved infrastructure

development, regulatory stability, and targeted investment incentives to enhance capital formation in the sector.

Keywords: Customs and excise duties, Corporate investment, Information technology, National information technology development levy; Telecommunications sector

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INTRODUCTION

Investment remains a critical driver of economic growth and structural transformation in both developed and developing economies. In particular, corporate investment plays a central role in expanding productive capacity, enhancing technological advancement, and improving competitiveness within strategic sectors of the economy (Acquah & Ibrahim, 2020). Governments therefore adopt various fiscal and tax policies aimed at mobilising revenue while simultaneously creating an environment that supports private sector investment. However, the interaction between taxation and investment outcomes remains a subject of persistent debate in economic and financial literature, especially in emerging economies where tax systems are often complex and multi-layered.

In many developing countries, including Nigeria, taxation serves dual purposes: revenue generation and economic regulation. While taxes are essential for financing public goods and infrastructure, they may also influence investment decisions by altering the cost of capital and expected returns (Opoku, Muazu, & Yakubu, 2019). Corporate taxation, in particular, has been widely associated with investment disincentives when tax burdens are perceived to be excessive or unpredictable. This concern is particularly relevant in Nigeria, where firms often operate under multiple tax regimes administered by different tiers of government.

The Nigerian economy has undergone significant structural changes over the past two decades, with the information and telecommunication (ICT) sector emerging as one of the most dynamic contributors to growth, employment generation, and innovation. The liberalisation of the telecommunications industry in 2001 marked a major turning point, leading to rapid expansion in mobile penetration, digital services, and investment inflows (Ejemeyovwi et al., 2019). The sector

has since become a backbone for financial inclusion, digital commerce, and productivity enhancement across other industries (David & Grobler, 2020).

Despite its growth potential, the ICT and telecommunications sector continue to face significant fiscal pressures arising from sector-specific and general taxation policies. Two key fiscal instruments that have attracted considerable attention are the National Information Technology Development Levy (NITDL) and Customs and Excise Duties. The NITDL, introduced under the National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) Act, imposes a 1% levy on the profit before tax of eligible companies with annual turnover above ₦100 million. The levy is designed to fund ICT development initiatives but has been criticised for increasing the effective tax burden on firms (Yusuf, 2022).

Similarly, customs and excise duties constitute a major component of Nigeria's indirect tax system. While customs duties are imposed on imported goods to protect domestic industries and generate revenue, excise duties apply to selected locally produced goods and services. Recent policy reforms have extended excise taxation to telecommunications services, thereby increasing operational costs for service providers (Peter & Ikechi, 2021). Given the capital-intensive nature of telecommunications infrastructure, such fiscal measures may have implications for investment decisions in the sector.

Empirical evidence on the relationship between taxation and investment remains mixed. Some studies argue that higher corporate taxes discourage private investment by reducing after-tax returns and cash flow availability, thereby constraining expansion activities (Sankarganesh & Shanmugam, 2023). Others suggest that the impact of taxation may be indirect or insignificant when other macroeconomic factors such as infrastructure, exchange rates, and regulatory quality dominate investment decisions (Jacob & Vossebürger, 2022). In the Nigerian context, findings have also been inconsistent, with some studies reporting negative effects of taxation on investment, while others observe weak or statistically insignificant relationships (Amahalu & Ezechukwu, 2022; Osegbue et al., 2021).

Theoretical perspectives, particularly the Free Cash Flow Theory, suggest that taxation may influence corporate investment by reducing internally available funds for capital expenditure and expansion. Firms with reduced free cash flow may experience constrained investment capacity, especially in capital-intensive industries such as telecommunications (Jensen, 1986). This theoretical foundation supports the argument that fiscal policy variables such as NITDL and customs/excise duties may have important implications for investment behaviour in the ICT sector.

Against this backdrop, this study examines the impact of the National Information Technology Development Levy and Customs and Excise Duties on corporate investment in Nigeria's information and telecommunication sector. The study seeks to provide empirical clarity on whether these fiscal instruments significantly influence investment decisions within one of Nigeria's most strategic and rapidly evolving sectors.

Literature Review

National Information Technology Development Levy (NITDL)

The National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) Act was enacted in 2007 to provide a structured legal and institutional framework for the development of information technology in Nigeria. The Act established NITDA as the regulatory and developmental body responsible for driving digital transformation across both public and private sectors of the economy. Its core mandate includes promoting the use of information technology in government operations, strengthening digital infrastructure, and setting standards for ICT development in Nigeria (Ezechukwu, Amahalu, & Okudo, 2022).

A key fiscal instrument introduced under this framework is the National Information Technology Development Levy (NITDL). The levy is imposed on companies with annual turnover of ₦100 million and above and is computed at 1% of profit before tax. It is collected by the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) on behalf of NITDA and remitted into a dedicated fund used for ICT development initiatives across the country (Yusuf, 2022).

From a policy perspective, the levy is designed to ensure that large corporate organizations contribute directly to national digital infrastructure development, innovation financing, and ICT capacity building. However, in practice, concerns have been raised regarding its potential impact on corporate profitability and investment decisions, particularly in capital-intensive sectors such as telecommunications. Firms in this sector often operate under high infrastructure costs, foreign exchange exposure, and rapid technological change, which makes additional levies potentially distortive to reinvestment decisions (Amahalu & Ezechukwu, 2017).

Although the levy is intended to support long-term economic digitalization, its short-term implication may include reduced retained earnings available for capital expansion, network upgrades, and technological innovation, thereby influencing corporate investment behaviour.

Customs and Excise Duty

Customs and excise duties represent long-established fiscal instruments used by governments to generate revenue, regulate trade, and protect domestic industries. Customs duties are taxes imposed on goods imported into or exported out of a country, while excise duties are levies placed on selected goods produced within the domestic economy, particularly those considered harmful or non-essential such as tobacco, alcohol, and related products (Inimino, Otubu, & Akpan, 2020; George-Anokwuru, 2023).

Beyond revenue generation, customs duties serve a protective function by making imported goods less competitive relative to locally produced alternatives. This policy tool is particularly important in developing economies that rely heavily on imports for industrial inputs, machinery, and consumer goods. Excise duties, on the other hand, are also used as corrective taxes to discourage consumption of socially harmful goods while simultaneously contributing to public revenue for development financing.

In Nigeria, customs and excise duties remain a significant component of non-oil revenue, reflecting the country's import-dependent industrial structure. Recent fiscal reforms have extended excise duties to cover telecommunications services, marking a significant shift in tax policy orientation (Peter & Ikechi, 2021). This development has generated debate among industry stakeholders,

particularly within the ICT sector, due to concerns that additional taxation increases operational costs and reduces sectoral competitiveness.

For telecommunications firms that rely heavily on imported equipment such as fibre-optic infrastructure, base stations, and network hardware, customs duties directly influence capital expenditure decisions. Higher import costs translate into increased project costs, delayed network expansion, and reduced incentives for large-scale infrastructure investment. Similarly, excise duties on services may reduce consumer demand indirectly, thereby affecting revenue streams available for reinvestment.

Corporate Investment

Corporate investment refers to the allocation of financial resources by firms toward assets and projects that are expected to generate future economic returns. These investments typically include capital expenditure (CAPEX), research and development (R&D), acquisitions, technology upgrades, and marketing-related investments (Panagiotidis & Printzis, 2021). Corporate investment is a central determinant of firm growth, competitiveness, and long-term sustainability.

From a financial perspective, investment decisions are influenced by expected profitability, cost of capital, regulatory environment, and macroeconomic stability. Firms invest when expected returns exceed the opportunity cost of capital, taking into account both systematic and unsystematic risks. However, investment decisions are also affected by fiscal policies, particularly corporate taxation and indirect taxes that influence retained earnings and cash flow availability.

Corporate investment is closely linked to firm value creation. When firms invest in positive net present value (NPV) projects, their market valuation increases, enhancing shareholder wealth. Conversely, excessive taxation can reduce internally generated funds, forcing firms to rely on external financing, which may be more costly or restrictive in emerging markets like Nigeria (Cohen, 2014).

Measurement of corporate investment varies across studies. Common proxies include capital expenditure scaled by total assets, aggregate spending on R&D and advertising, and net investment

calculated after accounting for depreciation and asset disposals (Opoku, Muazu, & Yakubu, 2019). In telecommunications firms, investment is particularly capital-intensive due to continuous network upgrades, spectrum acquisition, infrastructure deployment, and technology migration such as 4G and 5G expansion.

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in Nigeria

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) play a central role in modern economic development due to its capacity to enhance productivity, communication efficiency, and innovation. ICT encompasses a wide range of digital tools, systems, and platforms used for the creation, storage, processing, and dissemination of information (Moshood et al., 2020). These include mobile networks, internet infrastructure, satellite systems, cloud computing, and digital applications that support communication and business operations.

In Nigeria, ICT has become one of the fastest-growing sectors, significantly reshaping economic activity and social interaction. The liberalization of the telecommunications sector in the early 2000s marked a turning point, leading to increased competition, improved service delivery, and massive expansion in mobile phone penetration (Ejemeyovwi et al., 2019). This transformation expanded access to communication services and enabled millions of Nigerians to participate in the digital economy.

The sector has also facilitated the growth of digital financial services, e-commerce platforms, and online education systems. With increased smartphone adoption and expanding internet coverage, ICT has become a major driver of financial inclusion and entrepreneurial development (David & Grobler, 2020). Nigeria has also emerged as a leading hub for technology startups in Africa, particularly in fintech, agritech, and healthtech, attracting both domestic and foreign investment (Ishola & Olusoji, 2020).

Despite these gains, the ICT sector continues to face structural challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, high cost of imported equipment, regulatory uncertainty, multiple taxation, and foreign exchange volatility. These challenges influence investment decisions and may constrain

the pace of sectoral expansion. Consequently, fiscal policies such as NITDL and customs/excise duties play a significant role in shaping the investment climate within the sector.

Theoretical Review

This study is anchored on the Free Cash Flow (FCF) Theory, originally developed within the broader agency theory framework and popularized by Jensen (1986). The theory provides a critical lens for understanding how corporate taxation and fiscal policy influence investment behaviour, particularly in capital-intensive industries such as telecommunications.

Free Cash Flow refers to the cash available to a firm after it has met all operating expenses and made necessary capital investments required to sustain or expand its asset base. It represents discretionary resources that management can deploy for dividends, debt repayment, or reinvestment (Amahalu & Ezechukwu, 2017). From a financial perspective, free cash flow is a key indicator of firm liquidity, operational efficiency, and long-term financial sustainability.

Jensen's (1986) seminal argument in the Free Cash Flow Theory posits that firms with excess free cash flow are more likely to experience agency problems between managers and shareholders. This arises because managers may not always act in the best interest of shareholders when they control surplus resources. Instead of distributing excess cash as dividends or using it to retire debt, managers may invest in projects that yield returns below the firm's cost of capital, thereby destroying shareholder value. These inefficiencies are described as "overinvestment problems," where managerial discretion leads to suboptimal capital allocation decisions (Opoku, Muazu, & Yakubu, 2019).

A central implication of the theory is that external governance mechanisms such as debt financing and dividend policies can mitigate agency costs. Debt, in particular, plays a disciplining role because interest obligations and repayment schedules reduce managerial access to free cash flow. Similarly, dividend commitments limit the amount of retained earnings under managerial control. As a result, both mechanisms serve to align managerial decisions with shareholder wealth maximization objectives.

Within the context of taxation, the Free Cash Flow Theory becomes highly relevant because corporate taxes, levies, and duties directly reduce the amount of post-tax cash available for reinvestment. In sectors such as telecommunications, where investment is capital-intensive and continuous technological upgrading is required, reductions in free cash flow can significantly constrain expansion, innovation, and infrastructure development. Taxes such as the National Information Technology Development Levy (NITDL) and Customs and Excise Duties (CED) reduce retained earnings, thereby limiting internally generated funds available for corporate investment decisions.

Furthermore, taxation may indirectly intensify agency problems. When cash flows are reduced due to higher tax burdens, firms may increase reliance on external financing. This introduces additional monitoring by creditors, which may improve investment discipline, but it may also restrict strategic flexibility and slow down investment timing decisions. In emerging economies like Nigeria, where access to capital markets may be imperfect and borrowing costs relatively high, the reduction of free cash flow through taxation may have a stronger adverse effect on investment decisions.

The theory also acknowledges that not all reductions in free cash flow are negative. A decline in free cash flow may reflect increased capital expenditure in productive assets, which can enhance future profitability. However, when reductions are driven by high taxation rather than strategic reinvestment, they may weaken firm capacity to undertake value-enhancing investments (Jensen, 1986).

In summary, the Free Cash Flow Theory provides a strong conceptual foundation for this study by explaining how taxation policies influence corporate investment decisions through their effect on internally generated funds, managerial discretion, and capital allocation efficiency. It is particularly relevant to the Nigerian telecommunications sector, where firms face substantial capital demands, regulatory pressures, and multiple layers of taxation that collectively shape investment behaviour and long-term sectoral growth.

Methodology

This study adopts a quantitative research design in order to empirically examine the relationship between taxation variables and corporate investment in Nigeria's information and telecommunication sector. The quantitative approach is considered appropriate because it allows for objective measurement of variables, statistical testing of hypotheses, and generalization of findings based on numerical data analysis (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). This design also supports the use of econometric techniques to establish causal or associative relationships between fiscal policy instruments and investment behaviour.

The population of the study comprises all eight (8) quoted communication and information technology firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as at 31st December 2022. These firms include Airtel Africa Plc, Briclink Africa Plc, Chams Holding Company Plc, Computer Warehouse Group (CWG) Plc, E-Tranzact International Plc, MTN Nigeria Communication Plc, NCR (Nigeria) Plc, and Omatek Ventures Plc. These firms were selected because they represent the core of Nigeria's formal ICT and telecommunications investment landscape and are directly affected by the National Information Technology Development Levy (NITDL), Customs and Excise Duties, and other sector-related fiscal policies.

A purposive sampling technique was adopted in selecting the study sample. This non-probability sampling method is appropriate because it allows the researcher to focus on firms that meet specific inclusion criteria, particularly firms with consistent availability of financial statements and tax-related disclosures over the study period. The selection ensures that only firms with relevant and reliable data are included, thereby enhancing the validity and robustness of the empirical analysis.

The study relies exclusively on secondary data sources. These include annual financial reports of the sampled companies, audited financial statements, industry reports, publications of the Nigerian Exchange Group, Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) tax bulletins, National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) reports, scholarly journal articles, textbooks, and relevant newspaper publications. The use of secondary data is justified because tax and investment data are historical in nature and are best obtained from verified institutional records rather than primary survey instruments.

The study employs a multiple regression analysis technique estimated using the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method. This approach is appropriate for assessing the effect of multiple independent variables such as Company Income Tax (CIT), Value Added Tax (VAT), National Information Technology Development Levy (NITDL), and Customs and Excise Duties (CED) on the dependent variable, which is corporate investment in the telecommunications sector. The regression model enables the study to isolate the individual effect of each tax variable while controlling for the influence of other variables.

The general econometric specification of the model can be expressed as:

$$CI = f(CIT, VAT, NITDL, CED)$$

Where:

- **CI** = Corporate Investment (dependent variable)
- **CIT** = Company Income Tax
- **VAT** = Value Added Tax
- **NITDL** = National Information Technology Development Levy
- **CED** = Customs and Excise Duties

The functional model is further transformed into a linear regression form as follows:

$$CI = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CIT + \beta_2 VAT + \beta_3 NITDL + \beta_4 CED + \mu$$

Where:

- β_0 = intercept
- $\beta_1 - \beta_4$ = coefficients of explanatory variables
- μ = stochastic error term capturing unobserved factors affecting corporate investment

To ensure robustness of results, diagnostic tests such as normality, multicollinearity, heteroscedasticity, and autocorrelation tests are considered necessary in the empirical analysis stage. These tests help confirm the reliability and stability of the regression estimates.

Overall, this methodological framework provides a structured and statistically rigorous approach for evaluating how Nigeria's tax structure influences investment decisions within the telecommunications industry.

Results and Presentation of Data

The descriptive statistical results for the National Information Technology Development Levy (NITDL) indicate that the variable recorded a mean value of 5.90 and a median of 0.15, suggesting a distribution where most observations cluster around relatively low values, with occasional higher values influencing the average. The distribution exhibits a positive skewness coefficient of 3.29, indicating a long right tail, which implies the presence of a few unusually high observations within the dataset. The kurtosis value of 3.39 suggests a distribution that is slightly more peaked than a normal distribution, though still relatively close to mesokurtic behaviour.

The Jarque–Bera normality test, with a probability value of 0.03, indicates that the distribution of NITDL is marginally non-normal at the 5% significance level. This suggests that while the data approximates normality, there are observable deviations likely driven by extreme values. Overall, the pattern of results implies that NITDL values are heavily concentrated near the lower bound, with limited but influential high-value occurrences affecting the distributional shape.

For Customs and Excise Duties (CUEXDU), the descriptive statistics show a mean value of 170.55 and a median of 31.40, indicating a substantial divergence between the central tendency measures. This gap reflects the presence of high-value observations that significantly raise the average relative to the median. The variable exhibits a positive skewness of 2.77, confirming that the distribution is right-skewed, with a small number of large values stretching the upper tail.

In addition, the kurtosis value of 10.48 indicates a highly leptokurtic distribution, meaning the data is sharply peaked with heavy tails. This suggests a high concentration of observations around the central values but with pronounced extreme outliers influencing dispersion. The Jarque–Bera test probability of 0.00 confirms a rejection of the null hypothesis of normality, indicating that the distribution of CUEXDU is significantly non-normal.

Overall, the results show that both NITDL and CUEXDU exhibit non-symmetric distributions with notable skewness and outliers, although CUEXDU demonstrates a much stronger deviation from normality compared to NITDL. These distributional characteristics provide important context for interpreting the regression outcomes and indicate the presence of variability in fiscal policy variables affecting the telecommunications sector.

Table 1: The descriptive statistics of the study

	PIT	CIT	VAT	NITDL	CUEXDU
Mean	36.50	677.85	518.43	5.90	170.55
Median	33.03	289.55	272.65	0.15	31.40
Maximum	110.00	3348.75	2924.81	26.97	1605.17
Minimum	13.80	12.30	7.30	0.00	0.00
Std. Dev.	17.60	829.26	640.62	7.89	356.91
Skewness	2.39	1.622	2.20	1.15	2.77
Kurtosis	11.20	5.317	8.27	3.29	10.48
Jarque-Bera	112.64	19.86	58.91	6.75	108.37
Probability	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.00
Observations	30	30	30	30	30

Source: Authors' Computation using EViews 10, 2025

Correlation Matrix

This analysis examined the correlation matrix of six variables in Table 1: Private Investment in Telecommunications (PIT), National Information Technology Development Levy (NITDL), and Customs and Excise Duties (CUEXDU). It examined the correlation coefficients, identified significant relationships, and discussed the implications.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix

	PIT	CIT	VAT	NITDL	CUEXDU
PIT	1.0000				
CIT	-0.2885	1.0000			
VAT	-0.2559	0.9532	1.0000		
NITDL	-0.2979	0.9711	0.9041	1.0000	
CUEXDU	-0.2976	0.6703	0.4925	0.7003	1.0000

Source: Authors' Computation using EViews 10, 2025

Regression Results and Interpretation

The regression output presented in Table 2 provides an empirical assessment of the relationship between taxation variables and corporate investment in Nigeria's telecommunications sector. The coefficient of the logarithm of Company Income Tax (CIT) is -0.207529, indicating that a 1% increase in CIT is associated with approximately a 0.21% decline in corporate investment. This suggests an inverse relationship between corporate taxation and investment levels. However, the associated probability value of 0.5383 exceeds the 0.05 significance threshold, implying that the effect is statistically insignificant and cannot be relied upon for strong inference.

For the National Information Technology Development Levy (NITDL), the estimated coefficient is -0.024956, indicating that an increase in NITDL is associated with a marginal reduction in corporate investment. Specifically, a one-unit rise in NITDL corresponds to an estimated 0.025 decrease in investment. Despite the negative direction of the relationship, the p-value of 0.2295 confirms that the effect is not statistically significant, suggesting that NITDL does not exert a measurable influence on corporate investment within the sampled firms during the study period.

The coefficient for Value Added Tax (VAT) is 0.322143, implying that a 1% increase in VAT is associated with a 0.32% increase in corporate investment. This positive relationship suggests that

VAT may not necessarily discourage investment and could reflect broader economic activity or consumption-driven investment dynamics. Nevertheless, the p-value of 0.3462 indicates that the relationship is statistically insignificant, meaning the observed positive association lacks sufficient empirical strength for generalization.

Similarly, Customs and Excise Duties (CUEXDU) record a coefficient of $-8.15E-05$, indicating an extremely small negative effect on corporate investment. The p-value of 0.8135 shows that this relationship is highly insignificant statistically, confirming that customs and excise duties do not have a detectable impact on investment levels in the model.

The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.192993$) indicates that approximately 19.3% of the variation in corporate investment (PIT) is explained by the independent variables (CIT, VAT, NITDL, and CUEXDU). This reflects a relatively weak explanatory capacity of the model. The Adjusted R^2 of 0.063872 further reduces this explanatory power to about 6.4%, after adjusting for the number of predictors, suggesting that the model may suffer from omitted variable bias or limited variable coverage.

Diagnostic statistics, including the F-statistic, standard error of regression, log likelihood, and Durbin–Watson statistic, collectively indicate that the overall regression model is not statistically significant at conventional levels. This implies that the joint effect of the explanatory variables does not sufficiently explain variations in corporate investment, and observed relationships may be largely incidental rather than systematic. The Durbin–Watson statistic, however, suggests that there is no serious evidence of autocorrelation in the residuals, indicating that the model is reasonably stable in that respect.

In summary, the results reveal that although taxation variables exhibit both positive and negative relationships with corporate investment, none of these effects are statistically significant. The low explanatory power of the model suggests that investment decisions in the telecommunications sector are likely influenced by additional macroeconomic and institutional factors such as inflationary trends, exchange rate volatility, infrastructure quality, regulatory stability, access to

finance, and overall macroeconomic conditions, which are not captured within the current specification.

Analysis of Research Questions

Research Question 1:

In what way does the National Information Technology Development Levy (NITDL) influence corporate investment of information and telecommunication companies in Nigeria?

The empirical results indicate that the National Information Technology Development Levy (NITDL) has a negative relationship with corporate investment in Nigeria's information and telecommunication sector. Specifically, the estimated coefficient of -0.024956 suggests that increases in NITDL are associated with a marginal decline in corporate investment levels. This implies that higher levy obligations may exert some downward pressure on firms' investment decisions, potentially due to reduced retained earnings or constrained internal financing capacity.

However, despite the negative direction of the relationship, the p-value of 0.2295 is greater than the conventional 5% significance level. This indicates that the observed effect is not statistically significant, meaning that the influence of NITDL on corporate investment cannot be confirmed empirically within the study period. In practical terms, while the levy appears to exert a dampening effect on investment, the evidence is not strong enough to conclude that it is a consistent or dominant determinant of investment behaviour among telecommunications firms in Nigeria.

Research Question 2:

What is the effect of Customs and Excise Duties on corporate investment of information and telecommunication companies in Nigeria?

The results further reveal that Customs and Excise Duties (CUEXDU) exhibit a negative but extremely weak relationship with corporate investment in the telecommunications sector. The coefficient value of -8.15E-05 indicates that increases in customs and excise duties are associated

with a very small reduction in corporate investment. This suggests that, in economic terms, the magnitude of the effect is negligible, even though the direction aligns with theoretical expectations that higher taxation may discourage investment.

The associated p-value of 0.8135 is far above the 0.05 threshold, confirming that the relationship is statistically insignificant. This implies that customs and excise duties do not exert a measurable or reliable influence on corporate investment decisions within the sampled firms. The result suggests that investment behaviour in the sector is likely driven more by other macroeconomic or structural factors than by variations in customs and excise duty levels.

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One (H01):

The National Information Technology Development Levy (NITDL) has no significant effect on corporate investment in information and telecommunication companies in Nigeria.

The regression output shows that NITDL has a coefficient of -0.024956, indicating a negative association with corporate investment. This suggests that an increase in the levy corresponds with a slight reduction in investment expenditure. However, the probability value of 0.2295 exceeds the 5% significance level, confirming that the relationship lacks statistical significance.

Based on this result, there is insufficient empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis. Consequently, it is concluded that NITDL does not have a statistically significant effect on corporate investment in the Nigerian telecommunications sector. Although the direction of the relationship suggests a possible adverse effect, the weakness of the statistical evidence implies that the levy is not a strong explanatory factor for investment decisions in the sampled firms.

Hypothesis Two (H02):

Customs and Excise Duties have no significant effect on corporate investment in information and telecommunication companies in Nigeria.

The estimated coefficient of $-8.15E-05$ indicates a very slight negative relationship between Customs and Excise Duties and corporate investment. This implies that increases in these duties may be associated with a minimal reduction in investment levels. However, the magnitude of this effect is economically negligible.

The p-value of 0.8135 is substantially higher than the 0.05 significance level, indicating that the relationship is not statistically significant. As a result, the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. This leads to the conclusion that Customs and Excise Duties do not significantly influence corporate investment in Nigeria's telecommunications sector during the period under review.

Overall Interpretation

Taken together, the findings from both hypotheses suggest that although taxation variables exhibit expected negative signs in some cases, their effects on corporate investment are weak, statistically insignificant, and inconsistent. This indicates that corporate investment decisions in the Nigerian telecommunications sector are likely influenced more strongly by non-tax factors such as macroeconomic stability, infrastructure availability, exchange rate movements, regulatory certainty, and access to financing rather than direct tax burden variations alone.

Discussion of Findings

The empirical evidence from this study indicates that the National Information Technology Development Levy (NITDL) exhibits a negative but statistically insignificant relationship with corporate investment in Nigeria's information and telecommunication sector. This implies that, in directional terms, increases in NITDL are associated with reductions in corporate investment levels. Specifically, the estimated coefficient suggests that a one-unit increase in NITDL corresponds to approximately a 0.025 decline in corporate investment, reflecting a mild contractionary effect on investment behaviour.

However, despite this observed inverse relationship, the result is not statistically significant, indicating that the effect may be due to random variation rather than a systematic economic relationship. This finding suggests that while NITDL may impose a theoretical burden on firms'

cash flows, it does not exert a strong enough influence to meaningfully shape investment decisions within the sampled telecommunications companies during the study period.

This outcome is consistent with earlier empirical evidence, particularly the findings of Ososuakpor (2016), which similarly reported a negative association between taxation-related variables and corporate investment behaviour in Nigeria. However, it is important to note that the broader literature presents mixed and sometimes conflicting results, with some studies identifying significant negative effects, while others report weak or insignificant relationships. This divergence in findings may be attributed to differences in sample composition, methodological approaches, economic cycles, and sectoral variations across studies.

The results further reveal that Customs and Excise Duties (CUEXDU) also have a negative but statistically insignificant relationship with corporate investment in the Nigerian telecommunications sector. The coefficient indicates that increases in customs and excise duties are associated with a negligible reduction in corporate investment, suggesting that higher trade-related tax burdens may slightly discourage capital expenditure decisions. However, the magnitude of this effect is extremely small, indicating limited economic relevance.

Importantly, the relationship is also not statistically significant, implying that customs and excise duties do not exert a measurable or consistent influence on investment behaviour among the firms examined. This finding suggests that telecommunications investment decisions are likely driven more by broader macroeconomic and structural conditions rather than marginal changes in customs and excise duty rates.

In contrast, some prior studies, including Oyedokun (2022), have reported a significant negative relationship between customs and excise duties and corporate investment in the telecommunications sector, both in the short run and long run. These studies argue that higher import-related taxes increase the cost of equipment, infrastructure deployment, and technological upgrades, thereby constraining investment capacity.

The divergence between the current findings and earlier studies may be explained by differences in time periods, policy reforms, exchange rate conditions, import dependency levels, and firm-

level resilience within the sector. It is also possible that recent policy adjustments, market liberalisation, and technological efficiencies have reduced the sensitivity of corporate investment to customs and excise duty fluctuations.

Overall Interpretation

In summary, the findings of this study suggest that both NITDL and Customs and Excise Duties exhibit negative but statistically insignificant effects on corporate investment in Nigeria's information and telecommunication sector. While the direction of influence aligns with conventional economic theory which predicts that higher taxation may discourage investment the lack of statistical significance implies that these tax variables are not dominant determinants of investment decisions in the sector.

The study therefore highlights the presence of mixed empirical evidence in the literature, reinforcing the need for further investigation into sector-specific dynamics. Future research may benefit from incorporating additional explanatory variables such as macroeconomic stability, infrastructure availability, exchange rate volatility, regulatory quality, and access to credit, which may provide a more comprehensive explanation of corporate investment behaviour in Nigeria's telecommunications industry.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examined the impact of taxation, specifically the National Information Technology Development Levy (NITDL) and Customs and Excise Duties, on corporate investment within Nigeria's information and telecommunication sector. The empirical evidence generated from the analysis indicates that both tax variables exhibit negative but statistically insignificant relationships with corporate investment. This suggests that although increases in these tax obligations are associated with marginal reductions in investment levels, such relationships are not strong enough to be considered statistically meaningful within the context of the sampled firms and period of study.

The implication of this finding is that taxation, in its current structure and application within the sector, does not constitute a dominant determinant of investment decisions by telecommunication companies in Nigeria. While economic theory often suggests that higher taxes may discourage investment by reducing retained earnings and increasing operational costs, the results of this study indicate that such effects are relatively weak or overshadowed by other prevailing economic and structural conditions.

Overall, the study concludes that taxation alone does not significantly drive corporate investment behaviour in Nigeria's telecommunications industry, and therefore, investment decisions are likely influenced more strongly by other macroeconomic and institutional factors such as market conditions, infrastructure availability, exchange rate stability, access to finance, and regulatory certainty.

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Strengthening Non-Tax Investment Drivers

Government policy should shift greater attention toward strengthening non-tax determinants of investment. Priority should be given to improving infrastructure provision, particularly stable electricity supply, broadband expansion, and transport logistics, as these are critical enablers of sustained investment in the telecommunications sector.

2. Enhancing Regulatory Stability and Predictability

Regulatory uncertainty can discourage long-term investment planning. It is therefore important for government agencies to ensure a stable, transparent, and predictable regulatory environment that reduces compliance costs and encourages long-term capital commitment by firms operating in the sector.

3. Improving Security and Business Environment

The level of insecurity in certain parts of the country continues to pose risks to business operations and infrastructure deployment. Strengthening national security and protecting critical ICT

infrastructure will enhance investor confidence and promote increased capital expenditure in the sector.

4. Reviewing Tax Policy Harmonisation

Although taxation was found to be statistically insignificant in influencing investment in this study, the multiplicity of levies in the sector still presents administrative burdens. There is a need for greater harmonisation and simplification of tax policies affecting the telecommunications industry to reduce compliance complexity and improve efficiency in tax administration.

5. Encouraging Investment Incentives in the ICT Sector

Government may consider targeted tax incentives, investment allowances, or sector-specific reliefs to stimulate long-term capital investment, particularly in infrastructure expansion, innovation, and digital transformation initiatives.

6. Periodic Policy Evaluation

Tax and investment policies affecting the telecommunications sector should be subjected to regular empirical review and impact assessment to ensure alignment with national digital economy objectives and global best practices.

In summary, while taxation remains an important fiscal tool for revenue generation, its role in shaping corporate investment within Nigeria's telecommunications sector appears limited in this study. A more holistic policy approach that integrates fiscal stability with infrastructure development, regulatory efficiency, and macroeconomic stability is therefore essential for stimulating sustainable investment growth in the sector.

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